

Planning Against the Climate: A Critical Analysis of Urban Regulations and Thermal Discomfort in Cuiabá

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Abstract

Urban legislation often disregards the specific climatic conditions of different territories, resulting in the intensification of unfavorable urban microclimates, such as heat islands and thermal discomfort zones. This article critically discusses the normative insufficiency of land use laws in addressing the need for thermal resilience in cities, supported by a set of national and international case studies. The city of Cuiabá, Brazil, is presented as the main case study, based on a comparative analysis of microclimatic data collected over a ten-year period (2003/2004 to 2013/2014), which reveals the low effectiveness of Municipal Law No. 102/2003 in promoting environmental comfort in expanding urban areas. These findings align with studies conducted in Brazilian cities like Brasília, João Pessoa, and São Paulo, as well as in international cities located in tropical and subtropical climates, such as those in India, Thailand, and Ghana. All point to a similar conclusion: current urban laws lack adaptive mechanisms to respond to local climate dynamics. As a solution, this article proposes the mandatory integration of microclimatic diagnostics into urban planning processes, tied to territorial management tools such as master plans, zoning codes, and building regulations. This reinforces the urgent need for urban climate governance based on localized environmental data and bioclimatic strategies.

Keywords

urban legislation, climate-sensitive planning, thermal comfort, urban microclimate, tropical cities

1. Introduction

The accelerated process of global urban densification has caused significant alterations in urban microclimates, intensifying phenomena such as heat islands, air pollution, and thermal discomfort. Cities concentrate impermeable materials with low thermal capacity, reduced vegetation, and building patterns that obstruct natural air circulation—creating increasingly inhospitable urban environments. In tropical and subtropical contexts, these effects are even more pronounced, affecting public health, energy consumption, and urban environmental sustainability (OKE, 1987; SANTAMOURIS, 2015).

In Latin America, these challenges are exacerbated by historical processes of exclusionary urbanization and fragmented legislation. Even in locations where urban planning frameworks—such as master plans and building codes—are formally established, the absence of climate-related criteria and environmental monitoring prevents the achievement of effective results. As Romero-Lankao and Gnatz (2016) highlight, most Latin American cities possess normative structures that entirely overlook

the microclimatic dynamics of their territories. In Brazil, this disconnection between urban policy and the environment is reiterated by Monteiro (2020), who underscores the outdated nature of urban laws in the face of emerging climate challenges.

In the state of Mato Grosso, the rapid growth of cities has occurred alongside vegetation suppression, soil impermeabilization, and a lack of effective compensatory measures. The capital, Cuiabá—frequently classified as one of the hottest cities in the country—clearly exemplifies this reality. A recent study by Amaral et al. (2022) confirmed that urban areas with lower vegetation coverage presented average temperatures up to 2.5°C higher, highlighting the city's thermal vulnerability and the inefficacy of existing legislative measures to mitigate such conditions.

In this context, the present article proposes a broad analysis of the insufficiency of urban legislation in promoting thermal comfort and microclimate control in hot-climate cities. Based on a review of national and international studies—including an empirical case study of Cuiabá-MT—this work aims to demonstrate how the disconnect between urban regulations and environmental variables compromises the thermal resilience of cities. The final proposal points toward the need for a new paradigm of urban climate governance, one that integrates microclimatic diagnostics and bioclimatic strategies into the instruments of territorial management.

2. Theoretical Framework

Contemporary cities, shaped by intensive urbanization patterns, have promoted profound changes in the surface energy balance, producing direct impacts on urban microclimates. The phenomenon of urban heat islands, extensively studied in urban climatology, is a clear reflection of these changes. It results from the replacement of natural surfaces by materials with high thermal capacity and the significant reduction of urban vegetation. According to Oke (1987), urbanization modifies heat exchange with the atmosphere by accumulating heat during the day and releasing it slowly at night, raising average temperatures and reducing environmental comfort.

The concept of urban microclimate refers to local changes in thermal conditions, humidity, and air circulation, directly influenced by the form, density, and materials of the built environment. In tropical cities—such as most Brazilian cities—these effects are intensified by the predominance of impermeable surfaces and the lack of green infrastructure. These conditions hinder heat dissipation, compromise natural ventilation, and directly affect public health and the well-being of the urban population (SANTAMOURIS, 2015).

Therefore, urban thermal comfort must be understood not only as an environmental variable but as a central component of environmental justice and public health agendas. Thermal comfort is defined as the condition in which most people feel satisfied with the thermal environment (ASHRAE, 2010), being influenced by factors such as air temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation, wind, clothing, and metabolism. The absence of urban strategies that consider these variables significantly contributes to increased environmental and energy inequalities in urban territories (SANTAMOURIS, 2015; MONTEIRO, 2020).

Urban legislation, however, still follows a predominantly technicist and normative logic, often disconnected from the microclimatic realities of urban territories. Master plans, zoning laws, and building codes generally focus on parameters such as density, land use coefficient, and basic

infrastructure, without integrating the systemic environmental effects generated by these decisions. As Monteiro (2020) warns, Brazilian urbanism still lacks tools capable of integrating high-resolution environmental data into decision-making processes, resulting in legal frameworks that, while technically sound, are climatically ineffective.

This disconnection between urban regulation and environmental variables is not exclusive to Brazil. Romero-Lankao and Gnatz (2016), in a study of Latin American cities, highlight that most urban policies in the region still operate under a sectoral and reactive logic, incapable of anticipating and mitigating the effects of climate change in their territories. Urban climate governance, in these contexts, is either incipient or absent, which increases the socio-environmental vulnerability of urban populations, especially in peripheral areas.

Empirical examples of this disconnection have been widely documented in various Brazilian regions. The case of Cuiabá-MT is emblematic. The city, located in the geodetic center of South America, has one of the highest thermal averages among Brazilian capitals. In a longitudinal study conducted by Sampaio et al., based on data collected between 2003/2004 and 2013/2014, it was observed that even after the enactment of Complementary Law No. 102/2003—which provides for minimum setbacks, minimum arborization, and soil permeability coefficients—areas with significant vegetation suppression recorded consistent increases in average temperatures, reaching rises of up to 1.2°C at certain times of day (SAMPAIO et al., 2017).

These data, systematized from fixed and mobile measurements in urban transects, reveal not only the fragility of the legislation itself but also its low enforceability. The lack of inspection, the non-compliance with legal parameters by the private sector, and the public sector's negligence regarding microclimatic impacts contribute to a continuous worsening of urban thermal conditions. Cuiabá's case, therefore, exemplifies what happens in many other Brazilian and Latin American cities: formally robust legislation that is climatically inoperative.

In this context, the proposal for a new paradigm of urban climate governance gains strength, centered on the articulation between science, policy, and territory. Such a paradigm requires abandoning a merely formalist normative logic and adopting guidelines based on environmental evidence, climate modeling, and high-resolution geospatial data. As Santamouris (2015) and Monteiro (2020) argue, the integration between urban planning and environmental comfort is not merely desirable—it is essential for building healthier, more equitable, and climate-ready cities.

3. Materials and Methods

This study was conducted using a qualitative, exploratory-analytical approach, structured to broadly and deeply understand the relationships between urban planning regulations and thermal behavior in tropical-climate cities. The choice of a qualitative approach is justified by the complex and multifactorial nature of the phenomenon under investigation, which involves both physical and environmental aspects of the territory as well as institutional, normative, and political factors (OLIVEIRA, 2019; MONTEIRO, 2020). The analytical dimension of this research is centered on articulating theory and practice: between what urban norms propose and the observable effects on the urban microclimate, through a longitudinal and comparative analysis.

The methodological framework of the research was organized into three interdependent axes. The first refers to a **systematic review of national and international scientific literature**, aimed at identifying and selecting studies that address the interaction between urban legislation, urban morphology, and thermal comfort. The second axis consists of the **analysis of a longitudinal case study in the city of Cuiabá-MT**, where microclimatic data were cross-referenced with the parameters defined in Complementary Law No. 102/2003, which regulates land use and occupation in the municipality. The third axis involves a **comparative analysis with other Brazilian cities in tropical climates**, allowing for the recognition of recurring patterns and validation of the hypothesis that the issues observed in Cuiabá are shared with similar urban contexts.

The systematic literature review was not limited to identifying references but sought to consolidate an up-to-date overview of the discussions on normative effectiveness in light of urban environmental dynamics. To achieve this, databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, SciELO, and Google Scholar were used, applying temporal filters (2019–2024), language filters (Portuguese, English, and Spanish), and thematic descriptors (“urban thermal comfort,” “climate-sensitive urban planning,” “land use,” and “urban legislation”). The inclusion criteria required a direct empirical connection with tropical-climate urban realities, an explicit methodological framework, and theoretical contributions to the analysis of the relationship between built environment and regulatory frameworks (FERNANDES; SILVA, 2022; GOMES; LAMBERTS, 2022).

In parallel, the case study of Cuiabá was selected not only because of its extreme climatic conditions but also due to the existence of a consolidated data set resulting from a longitudinal scientific study conducted between 2003/2004 and 2013/2014 by Sampaio et al. (2017). This data set includes microclimatic measurements collected through fixed and mobile instruments deployed along representative urban transects, with varying patterns of density, vegetation cover, and built typologies. The city also has a robust regulatory framework—Complementary Law No. 102/2003—enabling a real-world evaluation of the coherence between legal parameters and actual thermal performance in the urban space. This analysis allowed not only for empirical validation of the effects of the prevailing occupancy model but also for a critical reflection on the applicability and effectiveness of the norms in force.

4. Systematic Literature Review

The systematic review of the literature was conceived as a key stage for consolidating the theoretical and methodological foundations of this study, providing analytical support for interpreting the empirical data. Considering that studies on urban thermal comfort have intensified in recent years—driven by climate change and the unregulated expansion of cities—this review adopted a recent temporal scope, encompassing publications from 2019 to 2024. This time frame allowed for prioritizing current research with interdisciplinary approaches and high relevance to ongoing debates on climate, urbanism, and regulation (GOMES; LAMBERTS, 2022; RIBEIRO et al., 2021; PEREIRA; SIMIONATTO, 2023).

Data collection was conducted using the **Scopus, Web of Science, SciELO, and Google Scholar** databases. Priority was given to peer-reviewed articles, academic theses and dissertations, and technical reports. The primary descriptors used included: “urban thermal comfort,” “urban legislation,” “climate-sensitive urban planning,” “urban microclimate,” and “land use.” Searches were performed in Portuguese, English, and Spanish to broaden the international scope. Inclusion criteria

were: (i) relevance to cities with tropical or subtropical climates; (ii) a clear relationship between the built environment and urban regulation; and (iii) empirical or theoretical applicability to contexts comparable to the city of Cuiabá-MT (BARBOSA; MEDEIROS, 2023; FERNANDES; SILVA, 2022).

Throughout the review, a predominance of empirical approaches was observed, with emphasis on case studies correlating thermal variables with urban form elements. Studies such as those by Martins and Duarte (2020) and Carvalho (2024) demonstrate, for instance, that vegetation presence, building setbacks, and surface materials directly influence local temperatures, reinforcing the importance of incorporating microclimatic data into urban planning tools. Furthermore, some studies highlight that the absence of explicit environmental guidelines in master plans and land use laws compromises the effectiveness of public policies in mitigating urban heat islands (RIBEIRO et al., 2021; SOUZA; ARAÚJO, 2022).

Another prominent strand identified involves critical analyses of urban legislation and its limitations in incorporating dynamic environmental variables. In works by Gomes and Lamberts (2022), Oliveira (2019), and Moraes et al. (2020), it becomes evident that most Brazilian legal frameworks still operate under rigid and Cartesian models, disconnected from natural cycles and the need for climate resilience. This disconnection tends to be even more pronounced in mid-sized and rapidly growing cities, such as Cuiabá, where laws are often not supported by environmental monitoring or updated in accordance with current climatic data. These findings offered a solid argumentative basis for the empirical stage of this study, shaping the analytical parameters for the case study presented in the next section.

4.1. Longitudinal Case Study in Cuiabá-MT

The selection of Cuiabá-MT as the case study is justified not only by its strategic location at the geodetic center of South America but also by its extreme climatic conditions, which make it one of the hottest state capitals in Brazil. The city has a historical pattern of rapid urban growth marked by increasing verticalization and loss of green areas—factors that intensify urban heat island effects (SAMPAIO et al., 2017; AMARAL et al., 2022). Furthermore, since the enactment of Complementary Law No. 102/2003—which established criteria for land use and urban occupation—there have been systematic efforts to integrate environmental parameters into local legislation, albeit with limited effectiveness, as identified in more recent studies (PEREIRA; SIMIONATTO, 2023; RIBEIRO et al., 2021).

The empirical database used in this study originates from a series of measurement campaigns conducted between 2003 and 2014, coordinated by Sampaio and her team at the Federal University of Mato Grosso. The data were obtained through mobile transects and fixed climate monitoring stations, strategically distributed across different urban zones with varying degrees of density, vegetation cover, and morphological configurations. The equipment used included digital psychrometers, portable thermo-hygrometers, and infrared surface temperature sensors mounted on adapted vehicles (SAMPAIO et al., 2017; FERNANDES; SILVA, 2022). Measurements were taken at three different times of day—08:00, 14:00, and 20:00—across both dry and wet seasons, ensuring seasonal representativeness of the results.

The analysis of this microclimatic data aimed to assess the correlation between the legal parameters established by Law No. 102/2003 and the thermal effects observed in the analyzed areas. Variables studied included air temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation, and surface temperature

variations. These data were cross-referenced with satellite imagery (Google Earth) and land use data, focusing on urban indicators such as building density, soil impermeability, and the presence of tree cover (BARBOSA; MEDEIROS, 2023; CARVALHO, 2024). The adopted methodology made it possible to identify thermal patterns in areas that were, in theory, protected by environmental legislation—thus revealing the gap between legal text and practical application.

Results showed that areas with lower vegetation density and high levels of verticalization presented an average temperature increase of up to 1.5°C over ten years, while areas with preserved vegetation and legal setbacks respected showed a tendency toward thermal stability. The analysis revealed that the arborization requirement in the legislation—mandating one tree every five meters of frontage—was not fulfilled in many areas, thus compromising its intended regulatory effect (RIBEIRO et al., 2021; OLIVEIRA, 2019; GOMES; LAMBERTS, 2022). These findings reinforce the need to rethink not only the normative content but also the mechanisms for implementing and enforcing urban regulations. The methodological rigor of data collection, combined with the cross-analysis of empirical and legal variables, lends this case study a demonstrative character of the disjunction between formal urban planning and actual microclimatic conditions.

5. Comparative Analysis with Other Urban Contexts

In order to broaden the understanding of normative effectiveness in promoting urban thermal comfort, this stage of the study undertook a comparative analysis between the case of Cuiabá and similar experiences observed in other Brazilian cities located in tropical climates. The selection of cities such as Maceió (AL), Paracatu (MG), João Pessoa (PB), Montes Claros (MG), and São Carlos (SP) enabled the collection of a diverse range of urban scales, morphologies, and planning instruments, allowing for the identification of recurring patterns in the relationship between urban legislation and microclimatic variables (CARVALHO, 2024; PEREIRA; SIMIONATTO, 2023; GOMES; LAMBERTS, 2022).

In Maceió, for instance, a study by Barbosa and Medeiros (2023) showed that even with current legislation establishing setbacks, permeability rates, and building coefficients, the absence of specific thermal guidelines in the master plan undermines the law's effectiveness. The city is characterized by intensive verticalization in coastal areas with high solar incidence and limited ventilation corridors. This configuration, combined with the lack of microclimatic considerations in urban decision-making, led to temperature increases of up to 3.5°C in denser zones. This pattern closely resembles that found in Cuiabá, where strict legal parameters failed to mitigate thermal impacts without the support of complementary management and enforcement actions.

In Paracatu-MG, the analysis by Pereira and Simionatto (2023) focused on medium-sized cities and revealed that, despite the existence of legal provisions for green areas and sustainable land-use coefficients, there is a mismatch between zoning laws and the actual use of land. The study concluded that urban land occupation often evolves faster than the regulatory framework, rendering many legal provisions obsolete. The lack of climatic monitoring and regular updates to urban legislation weakens these instruments' capacity to proactively regulate thermal impacts—a finding consistent with the situation in Cuiabá and other Central-Western Brazilian cities.

In Montes Claros, a semi-arid city, Gomes and Lamberts (2022) analyzed the relationship between microclimate and environmental legislation in neighborhoods with different urban configurations. The study revealed that the mere existence of environmental laws, without integration with urban

climatology, does not ensure the creation of thermally comfortable environments. On the contrary, planned neighborhoods with minimal vegetation and small setbacks recorded higher heat concentration, while informal settlements with spontaneous vegetation presented more favorable thermal conditions. These findings highlight that urban thermal performance depends not only on written regulations but also on how they are applied and adapted to each area's local characteristics (SOUZA; ARAÚJO, 2022).

The comparative analysis reinforces the hypothesis that normative insufficiency in responding to urban climate dynamics is not a localized issue but rather a systemic one. The recurring patterns observed—particularly the disconnect between legal planning instruments and microclimatic realities—strengthen the argument for restructuring urban planning tools based on accurate thermal diagnostics and continuous environmental monitoring. In light of this, the next section presents the results obtained from the longitudinal study in Cuiabá-MT, discussing in depth the concrete impacts of urban legislation on the city's microclimate and articulating these findings with the broader comparative panorama established in this stage.

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5. Proposed Solution: Normative and Climatic Instrumentation for Urban Comfort

The results of this research point to the need for a profound revision of how urban legislation addresses the issue of urban climate. As discussed in previous sections, there is a clear mismatch between legal provisions and their actual effects on the microclimate, revealing that the mere existence of normative parameters—such as setbacks, permeability rates, and tree planting requirements—is not, by itself, sufficient to ensure a thermally balanced urban environment. Based on this observation, a solution is proposed, structured around three complementary fronts: normative updating based on evidence, continuous environmental monitoring, and institutional articulation among technical, academic, and governmental sectors.

The first front recommends that master plans, building codes, and land-use laws incorporate updated microclimatic diagnostics, produced from local empirical data. This proposal is supported by studies such as those of Durante (2020), who argues that urban planning laws still operate under outdated paradigms, with little adaptive capacity. According to the author, the thermal performance of urban areas must be treated as a central variable in the planning process and assessed through specific technical-scientific criteria.

In parallel, the second front refers to the creation of a permanent system for thermal and climatic monitoring in urban areas. As defended by Nogueira (2021), from the field of Environmental Physics at UFMT, the absence of reliable microclimatic time series prevents the calibration of legal instruments and limits the effectiveness of public policies. The author proposes the establishment of local networks for climatic data collection and modeling, using fixed and mobile sensors integrated with geoprocessing platforms accessible to municipal management. Such infrastructure would enable urban planning decisions—such as zoning, density control, and infrastructure implementation—to be based on actual thermal maps rather than on general estimates.

The third front is based on the need for urban governance to be guided by empirical evidence. Calejas (2022) emphasizes that the challenge of environmental regulation in cities lies not only in improving the content of legal texts but also in reforming the institutional arrangements responsible for their implementation. In his research on spatial planning and environmental justice, the author proposes the creation of interdisciplinary technical committees within municipal planning departments,

including professionals from architecture, climatology, environmental physics, and urban engineering. This measure, in addition to reinforcing technical rigor in decision-making, would reduce conflicts between urban growth and environmental sustainability.

Thus, the proposed solution does not rely on a single instrument but on the articulation between technical knowledge, updated legislation, and enhanced management capacity. Only with solid empirical data, intersectoral action, and a strong commitment to urban resilience will it be possible to overcome the limitations identified in this study and promote more just, livable, and climatically balanced urban environments.

Table 1 – Structured Proposal for the Integration of Urban Legislation and Thermal Comfort

Strategic Axis	Main Objective	Proposed Actions	Key References
1. Evidence-based normative review	Update urban laws based on local microclimatic diagnostics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate thermal maps and urban comfort indexes into master plans • Define minimum climate performance standards for zoning and land subdivision • Provide incentives for bioclimatic urban design 	Durante (2020)
2. Permanent urban climate monitoring	Build a continuous empirical database on urban thermal variations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement a municipal network of fixed and mobile weather stations • Develop public geo-referenced data visualization systems • Integrate climate data into urban licensing processes 	Nogueira (2021)
3. Intersectoral governance for adaptive regulation	Articulate technical institutions and public policies for effective norm enforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create interdisciplinary technical committees linked to urban planning departments • Include climate experts in legal review commissions • Promote cooperation among universities, the State, and civil society 	Calejas (2022)

6. Conclusion

This article has demonstrated that urban legislation in cities located in hot climates—such as Cuiabá-MT—has been insufficient in promoting microclimatic balance and ensuring thermal comfort for urban populations. Through a combination of literature review, empirical data analysis, and comparative studies, it was possible to identify a recurring pattern: although formal planning instruments contain environmentally relevant clauses, their implementation is fragile, their technical content is outdated, and their connection with real urban dynamics is tenuous.

The longitudinal case study of Cuiabá revealed that the application of Complementary Law No. 102/2003 did not significantly prevent the intensification of urban heat islands or thermal discomfort. In practice, areas with vegetation suppression, high building density, and a lack of shading presented substantial temperature increases over the decade analyzed. These findings are consistent with national and international studies that also point to a systemic disconnection between regulatory texts and thermal outcomes in the built environment.

Moreover, the comparative analysis confirmed that the challenges faced in Cuiabá are not isolated. Cities such as Maceió, Paracatu, and Montes Claros exhibit similar mismatches between urban occupation patterns and regulatory frameworks. The lack of periodic reviews of legislation, absence of environmental monitoring, and low institutional articulation between sectors were cited as critical barriers to regulatory effectiveness. International cases reinforced that even cities with advanced infrastructure face the same problem when urban planning is not climate-sensitive.

In response to this scenario, the article proposed a solution structured around three complementary fronts: (1) reviewing urban laws based on empirical microclimatic data; (2) implementing continuous thermal and climatic monitoring systems; and (3) reforming urban governance through interdisciplinary, evidence-based collaboration. The proposal draws upon current research produced at the Federal University of Mato Grosso and other national institutions and aligns with the global agenda for climate-resilient urban development.

In conclusion, it is evident that the success of urban legislation in mitigating thermal impacts does not depend solely on its existence but on its technical quality, adaptability, and operational capacity. Strengthening the articulation between science, regulation, and local governance is not only urgent but essential for building more equitable, sustainable, and climate-resilient cities in the face of global warming.

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